

“POLITENESS STRATEGIES IN COMMUNICATION OF ENGLISH”

Sagdullayeva Setora Sagdulla qizi

Student, Uzbekistan State World Languages University

@setorasagdullayeva634.gmail.com

Annotation: The contemporary communication emerges in real life through various concepts and discourses. In linguistics, the categories of everyday communication include the system of norms, models of speech behavior and politeness. The goal of the article is to explore strategies of expressing politeness in communication of English. These strategies could present in various types according to the situation or urgency. Thus, they are analyzed in real life speech acts, like warning, requests, compliment.

Keywords: politeness strategies, bald on record, positive politeness, negative politeness, off-record politeness, implication.

Politeness is the most distinctive feature of communicative behavior of individuals. A famous anthropologist Kate Fox remarked that all English learners tended to be impressed by its courtesy, despite some complaint about English reserve. After some investigation about politeness strategies, it is concluded to be found four main principles to express politeness for different speech acts, such as inviting, making suggestions, requesting, responding and social behavior. Strategies in most conversational activities proposed by Brown and Levinson (1987) are bald on record, positive politeness, negative politeness and off record.

1) Bald on record strategy do not express more politeness factors in order to minimize the threat to the listener’s face. It is a direct way of saying opinions without reducing to the imposition, clear, unambiguous and concise way. It usually includes great urgency, requiring, task-oriented, alerting, welcomes, offers and speaking as if great efficiency is needed.

Here some examples are given for this strategy¹:

- a. Great urgency: Watch out!
- b. Speaking as if great efficiency is necessary: Hear me out: ...
- c. Task-oriented: Pass me the hammer.

This on record strategy is employed among the community who are very close or know each other very well. Urgent situation is proper for this strategy and maintaining face is not a vital aim of the communication. That is why if someone warn somebody by shouting “Watch out!”, it should not be impolite, but the urgency is more important in that dangerous situation. Other strategic manners also consider another important task than politeness.

2) Positive politeness strategy occasionally occurs in the group of people who have strong relationship of relativeness, friendship or knowing each other fairly well. Positive politeness attempts to pay attention to addressee’s interest, desire and goods. It consists of notice, attention to hearer; exaggeration; intensify interest to the hearer; use in-group identity marker; seek agreement; avoid disagreement; presuppose/ rise / assert common ground; joke; conveying that the speaker and the hearer are cooperators; assert or presuppose speaker’s knowledge of and concerns for hearer’s wants; offer, promise; be optimistic². Moreover, the strategy is used to give or ask for reason, assert reciprocity like giving presents, filling listeners’ desire by covering speaker and listener in the activity, too. Followings are exact examples for this situations:

- a. Notice and attention to the listener (interest, needs and goods): What a beautiful vase this is! Where did it come from?
- b. Exaggerate (interest, approval and sympathy): What a fantastic garden you have!

¹ Supriyanta, Imam Ghozali. An analysis of politeness of strategies used by Clarie Peterson in the boy next door movie. - Sarjanawiyata Tamansiswa University. –page 2.

² Brown, P. and Levinson, S. Some Universal in Language Usage. -Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1987. -pp 98-106

c. Intensify interest to the hearer: I never imagined that there were thousands of beautiful girls in John's party yesterday!

It is obvious that English countries tend to use the positive politeness strategies not only in written books, but also in daily English communication. However, the frequency of usage depends on the relationship between actors of conversation. The strategy emphasizes solidarity, common grounds and agreement. In research articles, in order to gain readers' attention author uses positive politeness when it is necessary to make claims or suggestions. Claiming common grounds and Showing that the writer and readers are two sub-strategies of writing under this strategy. According to Myers, writers utilize modifiers to intensify like adjectives of certainty, sure, doubt or definite, clearance.³

The second and third strategies of polite communication, positive and negative strategies, make use of redress activities to mitigate the face threatening actions which possibly threaten the faces of the interlocutors. Language users need these strategies to cater for their or other's face necessities as to strengthen the connection between them.

3) Negative politeness strategy is considered as the heart of respect behavior. It is more specific and focused (Brown and Levinson, 1987). It is opposed to positive politeness strategy that deals with people's need for social approval, not to be intruded or imposed upon. Everyone judge others themselves and suppose that they share obsessive need for privacy, thus in most cases, they mind their own business and politely ignore them (Hitchings, 2013). It is more consideration than unfriendliness in communication. Negative politeness could be conventionally indirect; question, hedge; be pessimistic; mitigate imposition; show deference; apologize; impersonalize. For more understanding of negative politeness, some examples should be seen:

a. Question, Hedge: Won't you open the door? (Which could be glossed as, "I request that you open the door")

³ Ebenezer Agbaglo. The Use of Politeness Strategies in the Analysis and Discussion Sections of English Research Articles. - Department of English, University of Cape Coast (UCC), Cape Coast, Ghana. Research on Humanities and Social Sciences. ISSN (Paper)2224-5766, Vol.7, No.9, 2017. pp 33-35

- b. Minimize the Imposition: Could I have a taste (a slice) of that cake?

The principles of negative politeness are essential parts of general communicative strategy that a communicant should respect the desire of the other, not to communicate or to interfere. Speakers prefer to use indirect speech by expressing interrogative construction or declarative rather than imperative mood to convey requests feeling. For instance, instead of using “Shut the door” in imperative mood, in interrogative form with a word “please” is more preferred: “Will you shut the door, please?” Subjunctive mood increases the degree of politeness: “Would/Could you shut the door, please?” the highest form of negative politeness is in an affirmative statement to express implicit request: “There is a draught here”, means a presupposition “Shut the door, please”⁴.

Negative politeness strategies are used by writers for the reason of avoiding imposing their views on readers. One method writers represent negative politeness is by being tentative by means of hedging (Getkham, 2013). Writers hedge by the means of modal auxiliaries, modifiers and tentative verbs. Basically, the modal auxiliaries are considered to be the verbs can, could, may, might, must, shall, should, will and would (Biber, 1999).

4) Off record politeness strategy is also indirect language that it removes the speaker from the potential to be imposed. In this position, the hearer must make an inference to recover what is intended. Likewise, it displays that if the speakers want to avoid their responsibility of doing face threaten acts, they can address the strategy. Off record strategies have the types: give hints; be vague; and be sarcastic; or joking. For example:

- a. Give Hints: It is cold in here.
b. Be Vague: Perhaps someone should have been more responsible.

This strategy, speaker wants to avoid responsibility, but wants to do a face threaten act. Off-record politeness relies upon implication. There exist fifteen off-record politeness strategies and they are: give hints, give association rules, presuppose,

⁴ Marina Ryabova. Politeness Strategy in Everyday Communication. -Kemerovo State University, 6 ul. Krasnaya, Kemerovo, 650043.- Russia, 2015. Pp 93-95

understate, overstate, use tautologies, use contradictions, be ironic, use metaphors, use rhetorical questions, be ambiguous, be vague, overgeneralize, displace hearer, be incomplete, use ellipsis⁵. Though off-record politeness strategies are considered very polite, Brown and Levinson remarked that in daily speaking, some of the off-record strategies are actually on record strategies. The intensity of face lost will be so high, when face threatening is done. Off- record strategies are usually used to give message ambiguously, leaving the listener to interpret the message in own way.

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⁵ Bousfield, D. Impoliteness in Interaction. Pragmatics & Beyond New Series. doi:10.1075/pbns. -2008.- pp 167